

On the Kinetics of Calcium Exchange from Ca-Soils by Ammonium and Potassium Chlorides in Aqueous Media

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The kinetics of calcium exchange from Ca-Soils prepared from 50 soil samples collected from semi-desert, arid, semi-arid, sub-humid, humid and per-humid soil-climatic regions of India, has been studied in presence of NH_4Cl and KCl solution in aqueous media. The study has been undertaken to find a suitable equation correlating the amount of exchangeable calcium (x) to be obtained at a particular interval of time (t) and the total exchangeable calcium (X). The following equation was obtained:

$$x = X - \text{anti log} \left\{ \log 10 X - \left[\frac{t}{2.303} \times \frac{5.2650 \times 10^{-1}}{X} \right] \right\}$$

This equation may prove useful where it is required to get an approximate idea about the amount of calcium expected to be available after a particular interval of time provided their total exchangeable calcium values are known in the soils of the climate regions considered and in presence of such fertilizer salts like NH_4Cl and KCl .

DE and Jee¹ were the first to use the method of kinetics for studying the calcium exchange from Ca-soils by ammonium and potassium chlorides in aqueous solution in order to obtain a relation between the exchangeable calcium obtained at a particular interval of time and the total exchangeable calcium when the fertilizer salts, NH_4Cl and KCl , are added. Theirs, however, was a preliminary study with only one sample of Gangetic alluvial soil and this study therefore, needed to be extended with a number of soils belonging to different soil-climate regions of India.

In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the calcium exchange from different Ca-soils by ammonium and potassium chlorides in aqueous solutions and to propose an equation relating exchangeable calcium obtained at a particular interval of time and the total exchangeable soil calcium. Attempts have also been made to observe how far the equation proposed tallies with that of De and Jee¹.

Experimental

Fifty soil samples belonging to Semi-desert, Arid, Semi-arid, Sub-humid, Humid-temperate and Per-humid, soil-climatic regions² have been collected for a depth of 0-15 cm. These soils were then airdried, pulverised and passed through 100 mesh (B.S.S.) sieve. These soils were chemically analysed for their total exchangeable calcium by the reported method³.

For the preparation of Ca-soil, 100 g. of each soil sample was taken in 1000 ml corning beaker and treated with *N*-calcium chloride solution. After keeping them overnight, next day, the mixtures

were filtered through Buchner funnel. The soils were leached four times with the same solution. Then the soils were washed with chemically pure distilled water and finally dried, with 50% ethanol. The soil left on the filter paper was then removed, dried, powdered and kept for experimentation.

For the determination of exchangeable calcium, 5 g of Ca-soil was taken in 100 ml volumetric flask and the volume was made up with either *N*- NH_4Cl or KCl solution. The flasks were then kept in a thermostat for equilibrium and calcium was determined volumetrically⁴ at intervals, 15, 30, 45 and 60 min in 25 ml aliquot of the solution. Similarly, the exchangeable calcium was determined in Ca-soils treated with *N*- KCl solution.

The k values (specific exchangeable rate of calcium) were determined by the following first order equation of Kinetics :

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log 10 \frac{X}{X-x}$$

where, k = the specific exchangeable rate of calcium,
 X = total exchangeable calcium,
 x = exchangeable calcium obtained at a particular interval of time, and
 t = time in minute.

Results and Discussion

The results presented in Table 1 and 2 show that with increase in the time of exchange there is no proportionate increase in the rate of exchangeable calcium. The amount of exchangeable calcium is

TABLE 1—KINETICS OF CALCIUM EXCHANGE FROM Ca-SOILS BY TWO FERTILIZERS VIZ., AMMONIUM AND POTASSIUM CHLORIDE IN AQUEOUS MEDIA

Soils belonging to different soil-climatic regions	Specific Exchangeable rate (<i>k</i>) of Calcium, ($k \times 10^{-2}$)							
	NH ₄ Cl				KCl			
	15	30	45	60	15	30	45	60
<i>Semi-desert</i>								
Jodhpur	6.52	2.53	1.05	0.59	9.56	1.35	0.69	0.27
Agra	8.57	3.19	2.13	0.91	13.58	3.70	2.44	1.66
Aligarh	5.15	2.22	1.29	0.82	5.12	1.87	1.14	0.84
<i>Arid</i>								
Allahabad	5.23	3.04	1.76	1.18	4.15	2.07	1.14	0.41
Farrukhabad	6.16	1.75	0.78	0.55	3.86	1.69	0.78	0.39
Fatehpur	7.44	3.43	1.79	0.66	3.35	1.48	0.79	0.45
Indore	8.36	3.38	2.21	1.34	7.03	2.57	1.45	0.82
Shivapuri	11.04	4.62	2.41	1.39	10.76	4.36	1.66	1.35
Mehsana	4.63	1.78	0.95	0.59	3.18	1.24	0.83	0.37
Dhulia	8.32	3.41	2.04	1.31	5.06	2.34	1.40	0.64
Nandar	10.71	4.27	2.85	1.33	3.27	1.54	0.47	0.46
Parbhani	6.76	2.78	1.67	1.17	8.38	3.31	1.96	1.01
Poona	6.78	3.00	1.00	0.51	6.54	2.97	0.96	0.48
Jalgaon	9.69	4.38	2.24	1.39	4.74	2.21	1.26	0.78
Nasik	3.25	1.52	1.02	0.49	3.35	1.39	0.93	0.38
Godavari	5.27	1.62	0.93	0.65	3.38	1.50	1.00	0.51
Guntur	8.30	3.39	2.06	1.29	3.97	1.54	0.98	0.66
Bangalore	6.74	3.03	1.84	1.10	3.79	2.64	1.66	1.07
Mandeya	5.86	2.31	1.51	0.86	2.70	1.35	0.58	0.29
Dharapuram	5.08	2.10	1.19	0.68	2.10	1.10	0.50	0.17
<i>Semi-arid</i>								
Azamgarh	10.60	2.28	1.17	0.92	7.97	1.84	0.74	0.64
Banda	7.54	3.56	2.51	1.31	12.62	3.58	2.44	1.10
Jhansi	5.15	1.17	1.62	0.82	4.64	1.96	1.09	0.65
Mirzapur	9.85	3.69	2.88	1.22	5.69	2.69	1.54	0.98
Lakshimpur-Kheri	10.38	4.30	2.31	1.22	32.29	4.29	2.33	0.57
Sultanpur	8.45	3.88	2.36	1.26	5.88	2.29	1.69	0.96
Varanasi	5.83	2.57	1.71	0.91	10.51	3.30	1.72	0.98
Jaunpur	1.96	0.77	0.33	0.31	4.47	1.90	1.27	0.78
Ghazipur	3.97	1.61	1.05	0.61	4.80	1.76	1.03	0.57
Bareilly	7.65	3.32	2.04	1.25	8.92	3.48	2.04	1.10
Dhanbad	4.50	1.97	1.26	0.85	2.43	0.72	0.25	0.19
Burdwan	7.44	3.13	1.83	1.18	6.72	2.39	1.27	0.45
Koraput	2.31	1.16	0.77	0.44	3.97	1.42	0.72	0.33
Gova	5.27	2.19	1.32	0.85	3.55	1.77	0.99	0.71
<i>Sub-humid</i>								
Dehradun	15.40	11.19	9.11	3.67	23.44	6.93	3.45	2.29
Nainital	2.29	1.14	0.57	0.36	3.43	0.93	0.62	0.26
Gorakhpur	14.18	5.14	2.94	1.00	7.63	2.44	0.99	0.64
Ranchi	7.46	2.58	1.36	0.83	6.54	2.73	1.66	1.06
Calcutta	5.91	2.17	1.45	0.82	14.04	2.10	1.18	0.71
Sibsagar	9.36	3.11	2.01	1.26	7.41	3.56	1.78	1.07
Nowgaon	4.46	1.90	1.26	0.76	3.02	1.65	1.08	0.58
Chamba	5.64	2.61	1.63	1.08	5.24	2.53	1.61	0.94
<i>Humid</i>								
Almorah	6.52	2.37	1.19	0.80	6.23	2.31	1.28	0.93
Mussorie	4.96	2.26	1.47	0.28	7.27	2.31	1.08	0.98
Ratnagiri	5.83	4.27	2.13	1.41	3.93	1.63	0.96	0.42
Nilgiri	10.06	3.78	2.23	1.52	6.07	2.83	1.84	1.02
Lakhimpur	20.73	7.07	4.53	3.25	73.58	13.25	3.88	1.99
Kerala	5.57	2.49	1.51	0.29	4.64	1.83	1.17	0.77
<i>Per-humid</i>								
Palampur	7.46	2.41	2.23	1.35	7.19	3.58	2.21	1.10
Darjeeling	7.44	3.46	0.83	1.12	4.29	1.77	1.04	0.61

TABLE 2—RELATION BETWEEN EXCHANGEABLE CO-EFFICIENTS (*K*) AND EXCHANGEABLE CALCIUM

Soil	Total Exch. Ca ⁺⁺ meq/100 g.	NH ₄ Cl		KCl	
		$\Sigma k/4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($k \times 10^{-2}$)	<i>K</i> ($K \times 10^{-2}$)	$\Sigma k/4 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($k \times 10^{-2}$)	<i>K</i> ($K \times 10^{-1}$)
<i>Semi-desert</i>					
Jodhpur	4.50	2.67	1.20	1.47	0.66
Agra	19.80	3.70	7.32	5.34	10.57
Aligarh	12.50	2.37	2.96	2.14	2.68
<i>Arid</i>					
Allahabad	13.00	2.80	3.64	1.94	2.52
Farrukhabad	17.60	1.31	4.06	1.65	2.90
Fatehpur	5.60	3.33	1.86	1.52	0.85
Indore	25.10	3.82	9.59	2.69	7.43
Shivapuri	37.00	4.86	17.98	4.33	16.76
Mehsana	5.80	1.68	4.59	1.41	0.82
Dhulia	12.50	3.78	4.73	2.61	3.26
Nandar	27.30	4.29	1.31	1.56	4.26
Parbhani	18.90	3.07	5.80	3.66	6.92
Poona	10.50	2.82	2.96	2.74	2.88
Jalgaon	26.00	4.42	11.49	1.24	5.83
Nasik	7.60	1.57	1.19	1.51	1.15
Godavari	8.80	2.11	1.86	1.59	1.40
Guntur	22.40	3.76	8.42	1.54	3.45
Bangalore	18.10	3.18	5.75	2.79	5.05
Mandiya	6.00	2.64	1.58	1.23	0.74
Dharapuram	7.50	2.26	1.70	0.96	0.73
<i>Semi-arid</i>					
Azamgarh	3.90	3.69	1.43	2.75	1.07
Banda	10.50	3.74	3.93	4.93	5.18
Jhansi	9.50	2.06	1.96	2.08	1.98
Mirzapur	31.00	4.21	13.00	2.72	8.43
Lakhimpur-Kheri	25.50	4.55	11.60	9.87	25.17
Sultanpur	22.20	3.99	8.05	2.70	5.45
Varanasi	18.90	2.75	5.20	3.86	7.30
Jaunpur	3.90	1.82	0.70	2.11	0.82
Ghazipur	7.80	1.81	1.41	2.03	1.58
Bareilly	16.00	3.50	5.60	3.88	7.76
Dhanbad	22.30	2.14	4.77	0.92	2.03
Burdwan	8.20	3.39	2.79	2.71	2.22
Koraput	5.80	1.17	0.68	1.62	0.94
Gova	11.20	2.41	2.68	1.76	1.96
<i>Sub-humid</i>					
Dehradun	16.00	9.84	15.74	9.02	14.43
Nainital	24.50	1.09	0.49	1.31	0.60
Gorakhpur	7.50	5.82	4.36	2.92	2.19
Ranchi	25.00	3.06	7.65	2.99	9.48
Calcutta	7.50	2.58	1.94	4.51	3.38
Sibsagar	35.20	3.94	13.87	3.46	12.18
Nowgaon	9.20	2.10	1.93	1.78	1.64
Chamba	18.40	2.68	19.76	2.58	4.75
<i>Humid</i>					
Almorah	6.10	2.72	1.65	2.69	1.64
Mussorie	6.30	1.99	1.25	2.91	1.83
Ratnagiri	21.90	3.41	7.47	1.73	3.79
Nilgiris	24.30	4.39	10.67	2.94	7.14
Lakhimpur	9.20	0.89	8.18	25.18	23.09
Kerala	15.20	2.62	3.98	2.10	3.19
<i>Per-humid</i>					
Palampur	16.40	3.61	5.92	3.52	5.77
Darjooling	9.10	3.46	3.15	1.92	1.75
		$\Sigma K/3 \text{ (m.e. min}^{-1}\text{)}$		$\Sigma [K/3]_{0.5} \text{ m.e. min}^{-1}$	
		NH ₄ Cl	KCl		
		5.56×10^{-1}	4.97×10^{-1}	or $[10.53 \times 10^{-1}]_{0.5}$ 5.2650×10^{-1}	

therefore, influenced by the total exchangeable calcium of the experimental soils. The phenomenon, therefore, can be well defined by the following simple equation of the first order of kinetics :

$$k = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{X}{X-x} \quad \dots (i)$$

The equation speaks well about the relation between the k values and total exchangeable calcium (X) and the exchangeable calcium (x) obtained at a particular interval of time.

The different k values obtained have been shown in Table 1. It may be seen that all calcium soils irrespective of the soil-climate regions record the specific exchangeable rate (k) of calcium, to the order of 10^{-2} . For the soils considered the order appears to be independent of the nature of salts used to exchange calcium. De and Jee¹ however, found a change in the order of the k values from 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} with the difference in the nature of the soil. This appears to be due to the fact that they used a small number of soil samples.

The orders show that the specific exchangeable rate of the calcium decreases with increasing amounts of total exchangeable calcium (cf. Table 1 and Table 2). In other words, as pointed out by De and Jee¹, the true exchangeable coefficient of calcium K can be obtained from the relation :

$$X = K \cdot \frac{1}{k} \quad (ii)$$

In Table 2, the values of $\Sigma K/3$ in both the salts is of the order of 10^{-1} and is not much different from the order obtained under $\Sigma[\Sigma K/3]_{0.5}$. It may thus be observed that this latter value being independent of every variable considered in the present experiment, is thus more of universal nature and may be incorporated in equation (ii) in the manner :

$$\frac{5.2650 \times 10^{-1}}{X} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{X}{X-x} \quad \dots (iii)$$

Following equation is obtained from the above calculation

$$x = X - \text{antilog} \left\{ \log_{10} X - \left[\frac{2.303}{t} \cdot \frac{5.2650 \times 10^{-1}}{X} \right] \right\} \quad \dots (iv)$$

where

x = exchangeable calcium at particular interval of time;

X = total exchangeable calcium, and

t = time in minute.

However, De and Jee¹ proposed a similar equation which is of the same order as obtained by us :

$$x = X - \text{antilog} \left\{ \log_{10} X - \left[\frac{t}{2.303} \cdot \frac{1.52 \times 10^{-1}}{X} \right] \right\}$$

It may thus be said that the equation proposed by De and Jee relating to exchangeable soil calcium (x) to be obtained after certain interval of time with the total exchangeable calcium (X) is not much different from that we have obtained considering larger number of soils than they used.

The equation (iv) proposed may well be used for the determination of the amount of exchangeable soil-calcium at a particular interval of time and when such fertilizer salts like ammonium and potassium chlorides are added to soils provided the total exchangeable calcium value of the soil is known. This may naturally save much of time, labour and money where the large number of samples are required to be analysed for their exchangeable calcium at a particular interval of time.

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